

Detection of the effect of some resistance antibiotics on *Staphylococcus aureus* isolated from urinary tract infections and molecular investigation of the *clfA* gene encoding the biofilm

362

Detección del efecto de algunas resistencias a antibióticos sobre *Staphylococcus aureus* aislado de infecciones del tracto urinario e investigación molecular del gen *clfA* que codifica la biopelícula

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Abstract

One of the human pathogens that spreads the most is *Staphylococcus aureus*. Because of the damage it does to life and, by extension, the economy, it became imperative to ascertain its prevalence and antibiogram in our surroundings in order to implement appropriate management and treatment. Records of microbiological cultures and outcomes of antibiotic sensitivity testing for possible UTI cases.

The results led to the conclusion that every *S. aureus* isolate tested positive for the *clfA* gene. The results showed resistance to Benzylpenicillin 100%, oxacillin 100%, gentamicin 40%, tobramycin 40%, levofloxacin 80%, erythromycin 100%, clindamycin 100%, trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole 60%, and tetracycline 60% acid at 80%. In other words, *Staphylococcus aureus* in UTI is resistant to most antibiotics, and the best antibiotic used during the study, bacteria sensitive to it is gentamicin, which is considered the lowest percentage of resistance compared to the rest of the antibiotics used during the current study.

Keywords: *Staphylococcus aureus*, VITEK, Antibiotic, Resistance, *clfA*.

Resumen

Uno de los patógenos humanos que más se propaga es el *Staphylococcus aureus*. Debido al daño que causa a la vida y, por extensión, a la economía, se hizo imperativo conocer su prevalencia y antibiograma en nuestro entorno para implementar un manejo y tratamiento adecuado. Registros de cultivos microbiológicos y resultados de pruebas de sensibilidad a antibióticos para posibles casos de ITU.

Los resultados llevaron a la conclusión de que todos los aislados de *S. aureus* dieron positivo para el gen *clfA*. Los resultados mostraron resistencia a bencilpenicilina 100%, oxacilina 100%, gentamicina 40%, tobramicina 40%, levofloxacina 80%, eritromicina 100%, clindamicina 100%, trimetoprim-sulfametoxazol 60% y tetraciclina 60% ácido al 80%. En otras palabras, *Staphylococcus aureus* en ITU es resistente a la mayoría de los antibióticos, y el mejor antibiótico utilizado durante el estudio, las bacterias sensibles a él es la gentamicina, que se considera el porcentaje más bajo de resistencia en comparación con el resto de los antibióticos utilizados durante el presente estudio.

Palabras clave: *Staphylococcus aureus*, VITEK, Antibiótico, Resistencia, *clfA*.

Staphylococcus aureus is Gram-positive according to Burke 's classification, as it is distinguished from other types of *staphylococci* as being coagulase-positive, and it is one of the most widely pathogenic types of *staphylococci* in humans (George *et al.*, 2004). *S. aureus* is defined as spherical cells with a diameter of 1 µm. Almost non-motile, uncoupled, and non-spore forming. It can grow well in most agricultural media and at optimum temperatures (30-37)C° and under facultative anaerobic conditions, but it grows better in aerobic conditions (Al-Toumi *et al.*, 2013). The cultivar characteristics of these bacteria are in the form of circular, slightly convex colonies with smooth surfaces. The color of the mannitol acri center was also observed to change color in the areas surrounding the growing colonies from pink to golden yellow; This is due to the presence of the red phenol reagent, which indicates the ability of this bacteria to ferment mannitol sugar (Al-Saadi *et al.*, 2014).

S. aureus is a typical component of human flora., as it appears on the skin, mucous membranes, upper respiratory tract, and in the air and soil. Carriers of the type *S.aureus* are estimated at 30% in the front of their nostrils, but it is one of the germs that can cause infections. Dangerous when there is an imbalance or disturbance in the host's immune defenses, and this percentage increases for people working in hospitals (Tong, 2012). Community infections are acquired spontaneously by strains carried in the nostrils or on the surface of the skin or both, while hospital infections can occur through single-cell acquisition of *S. aureus* strains. Common in patients who underwent surgery or patients infected with this bacterium. Among the most significant sources of Patients that are affected are the ones who transmit the sickness, which may be transmitted directly to other patients through the hands of people working in the hospital, as the hospital environment is a major source of severe infections that, after the healing process, turn into latent cases, and bacteria often transform from the active state to Silent bacteria, which helps it to move to the surrounding environment and expand its spread (Warshawsky *et al.*2000). One of the primary causes of nosocomial infections is *S. aureus.*, especially MRSA strains, since several investigations have shown that 40% of *S. aureus* isolates are methicillin-resistant., and this percentage increases year after year, and many studies have documented the increased mortality rate caused by MRSA strains in various countries of the world, the cause of these deaths. It possesses many virulence factors in addition to its resistance to many antibiotics, unlike MSSA strains, which are sensitive to methicillin (AL-Sheikh and yousif , 2014).

S. aureus One of the most clinically important *staphylococcal* bacteria the disease is caused by *S. aureus* itself or by the production of toxins and extracellular substances whose wall consists of peptidoglycan and lipoteichoic acid and many toxic and secreted products that are likely to be involved in the virulence of these bacteria (Tong *et al.*, 2012; Al-Saadi *et*

al., 2014). Pathological infection of this bacterium occurs when it enters the tissues through abrasions or wounds, or when it comes into contact with the surface of the skin tissues of the host. Which helps in the spread of bacteria, which works to break down the basic material of the connective tissue (Janštová *et al.*, 2012). These bacteria cause skin infections such as boils, pimples, abscesses, and impetigo, as well as wound infections. *S. aureus* bacteria can enter. It is one of the most important bacterial types involved in nosocomial infections, as reports of the National nosocomial infection surveillance indicated a significant increase in the rate of infection with these staphs, which may reach 70% (jasim,2012). These bacteria also cause infections in the pharynx, which, if repeated, lead to complications such as rheumatoid arthritis, lung suppurations and abscesses, upper respiratory infection, Nasal fruncles, Pneumonia, Endocarditis, Otitis (Al-Toumi *et al.*, 2013).

Antibiotics

Antibiotics are chemicals produced by several microorganisms, including bacteria and fungi. It forms a part of special or modified secondary metabolites that have activity against different groups of microorganisms. They are also known as organic chemicals produced by different microorganisms. (Prescott *et al.* , 2005) . Penicillin is the first antibiotic that was discovered by chance by Fleming in 1928, who noticed the inhibition of the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus* by the fungus *Penicillium notatum* (Torok *et al.*, 2010).

Macrolide are one of the most important families of antibiotics, For its importance in the management of bacterial infections, including Gram-positive and Gram-negative, which are caused by *Streptomyces* or *Arthrobacter* bacteria. Macrolide ingredients are used as an alternative treatment for people allergic to β-lactam. Macrolide group includes a number of antibiotics, including: erythromycin, azithromycin, clarithromycin, spiramycin, oleandomycin, roxithromycin, jozathromycin. (Kwiatkowska and Maslinska, 2012, Mankin, 2008).

Erythromycin it is the first antigen of the macrolide group discovered from *Streptomyces erythraeus*. It has anti-bacterial activity and kills them if it is of high concentration. It was used in the early 1950s to treat respiratory infections in addition to skin and soft tissue infections. Erythromycin has a spectrum similar or slightly wider than extended-spectrum penicillin, and for that reason, those who are allergic to penicillin antagonists take it, the benefit of erythromycin is that it kills a variety of infections., including intracellular pathogens such as *Legionella* and *Mycoplasma* and *Chlamydia* (Zuckerman, 2004; Katzung, 2009).

Azithromycin it is of the azalid class. Azalid is derived from Macrolide, meaning the azalid class is a class of Macrolide that contains a nitrogen molecule in the Macrolide ring, which affects the pharmacokinetics

and increases the stability and stability of the antibody molecule. Azithromycin is used to treat or prevent some bacterial infections, most of which cause otitis media. Tonsillitis, Laryngitis, Bronchitis, Pneumonia, Sinusitis, and in recent years it has been used to prevent bacterial infections in newborns who have a weak immune system, in addition to the ability of Azithromycin to eliminate some urinary tract infections and diseases. (Zuckerma, 2004).

Clindamycin It is an antibiotic of the Lincosamides family, its composition was first announced in 1966 by Magerlein and Birkenmeyer Numerous illnesses brought on by both anaerobic and aerobic Gram-positive bacteria are treated with this antibiotic., and it is also used to treat parasitic infections such as malaria, methods to handle regional infections. Additionally, methicillin-resistant *staphylococci* (MRSA) respond well to it. It was first put on the market in 1968 (Drinkovic, 2001).

Antibiotic resistance

Antibiotic resistance by some microorganisms is a dangerous indicator of human health, especially its direct impact on increasing the rate of infections. The spread of the disease and consequently an increase in the death rate in addition to an increase in the costs of manufacturing antibiotics (Najeeb, 2011). The emergence of bacterial strains that are resistant to the currently used antibiotics and their rapid increase is a source of concern all over the world, and what makes this problem worse is that this resistance is not limited to a specific antibiotic, but rather extends to include all compounds of the same type (Murti, 2011). WHO experts confirmed that antibiotic resistance has become a global problem, as it has become easy to transmit between countries and even between continents. Therefore, bacterial resistance to antibiotics has been called the “Nightmare Bacteria” nightmare. roughly 2 million Americans get illnesses that are resistant to one or more of the medications used to treat them, and each year, roughly 23,000 Americans pass away due to bacterial resistance to antibiotics. (Frieden, 2013). Beta- lactams are also resistant to many other antibiotics plus _ ESKAPE group “*Enterococcus faecium*, *S. aureus*, *Klebsiella Pneumonia*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* , *Enterobacter species*. Despite the introduction of several new types of antibiotics during the past decades, many negative factors prevented a decrease in the incidence of infection. These bacteria are a result of the high price of these antibiotics as well as the development of novel resistance mechanisms., as several modern antibiotics are being developed to combat infections caused by MRSA strains, while most of these antibiotics will be directed to combat acute skin infections ABSsIs Rodvold (Senthamilselvi *et al*, 2012). The microorganism resorts to resistance to antibiotics by many means, including the production of degrading enzymes capable of analyzing the antibody molecule, or making modifications in it to inert molecules, or preventing the antibody from reaching the target it affects, or reducing the concentration of the antibody by

expelling it outside the body through a mechanism called Efflux pump (Al-Qaisi and *et al*, 2007).

Characters of resistance _ nongenetic resistance:

It may be caused by the absence of the target site, for example, penicillins affect the peptidoglycan available in bacteria only, so it is not expected to affect fungi, and some organisms can lose the target that is affected by the drug after several generations of growth in the presence of the drug and thus become resistant, for example, bacteria lose some components Its cell wall transforms into the filamentous L-Form during penicillin administration and becomes resistant to it. The other resistance is the failure of the antibiotics to reach their goals as a result of the exudation barriers (Brooks *et al.*, 2010).

Genetic resistance: is divided into

- **Chromosomal resistance:** can occur as a result of spontaneous genetic mutations in the site that is affected by the drug, so it works in the presence of the drug and the latter acts as a selective factor, encouraging resistant cells and killing sensitive ones. In particular, the resistance of bacteria increases as a result of the presence of antibiotics in the vicinity of cells, which makes them under great stress, so they show a high susceptibility to mutagenicity (Al-Khafaji, 2008).
- **A chromosomal genetic resistance:** symbolized by the appearance of transposons and plasmids, two examples of mobile genetic components, which usually encode for enzymes that disintegrate antibiotics. Bacteria often contain independent genetic elements and are in the form of genetic elements divided in closed circular rings called plasmids , they have sites of origin , especially The R-plasmid is transmitted in more than one way, Gram-negative bacteria exchange these factors by conjugation, and Gram-positive bacteria exchange these factors by transduction or transformation, and genes can move from a plasmid to Other, depending on the Rec A protein or the jumping process for jumping genes (Al-Khafaji, 2008). As for the transposonal elements, they are segments of DNA that have the ability to transfer information from one location inside a DNA molecule to another, or even to another DNA molecule. Plasmids and chromosomes are additives to them. There are three types of jumpers in bacteria, which are the insertion sequence elements and the transposons. Transposon and some special viruses, insertion elements are the simplest types of transposable elements that do not carry genetic information for their movement within the chromosome. As for transposable genes, they spread in the genomes of living things and can be stuck in certain sites or randomly, some of them are simple and the other is

complex, and most of them carry the character of resistance to antibiotics (Madigan *et al.*, 2012).

By promoting cell-to-cell attachment, polysaccharide intracellular adhesion, which is generated by the *icaADBC* operon controls how *S. aureus* biofilms grow. Additionally, surface-associated proteinaceous adhesins may be crucial for the adhesion, colonization, and biofilm formation of *S. aureus*. Clumping factor A, or *clfA*, Many microbial surface components that are capable of identifying sticky matrix molecules can be expressed by a gene, such as clumping factors A and B. (Eyoh *et al.*, 2014). Regarding the development of biofilms and their toxicity, Infections of the urinary system caused by *S. aureus* remain mysterious. Many scientists have recently concentrated on the investigation of genes involved in the production of biofilms and their importance in *S. aureus* infections. (Ando *et al.*, 2004).

The importance of biofilm-related genes in the formation of biofilms and the rise in antibiotic resistance has led to an increase in the demand for more study. Consequently, the formation of biofilms and the emergence of antibiotic resistance in *S. aureus* isolates from UTIs were the primary goals of the current investigation.

Collection of Samples

Samples were collected from patients admitted to (Baquba Teaching Hospital). The patient was asked if he was taking antibiotics, then samples were taken according to the type of infection. Samples were taken from urine as a result of urinary tract infection, in sterile test tubes and bottles.

Preparation of culture media:

The culture media and dyes were prepared based on the sources used in the study and according to the manufacturer's instructions. The media was sterilized with an autoclave at a temperature of 121 °C for a period of 15 minutes and at a pressure of 15 pounds / in². As for the glass materials, they were sterilized in an oven at a temperature of 180°C for a period of two hours (Ryan and Ray, 2004).

Samples culture

Samples were planted on blood agar medium and Maconkey agar medium, and the isolates were purified on blood agar medium and saline mannitol by plating method, and all dishes were incubated aerobically at 37°C for 24 hours, after which a number of phenotypic and biochemical diagnostic tests were performed for the bacteria in question (Macfaddin, 2000) .

Diagnosis of Bacteria

The obtained isolates were diagnosed according to the following bases:

Morphological Characteristics

The phenotypic characteristics of the isolates were studied on the media of the nutrient agar and the blood agar in terms of colony shape, size, color, edges, opacity, texture and others. The phenotypic characteristics of the cells were also studied by making dry swabs for direct microscopic examination to observe the cells' shape, regularity and interaction with Gram stain.

Biochemical Tests

Before conducting the tests, the bacteria were activated on the medium of the solid infusion of the heart and brain, and the medium of the blood agar. The diagnostic tests contained in to diagnose isolates to the species level, (Forbes *et al.*, 2007) which included the following:

1. Catalase Test
2. Coagulase Production Test Coagulase
3. Coagulase Test
4. Test urease production
5. Citrate Utilization Test
6. Growth test in mannitol salt agar medium

Diagnostics with the VITEK 2 Compact System

I made use of VITEK 2 from Bio Merieux. This device has 64 biochemical tests that are used to diagnose germs, allowing for the performance of biochemical tests for bacterial isolates, increasing the degree of diagnostic accuracy. Yeast, that is. also performing 99% of antibiotic sensitivity tests Pinch (2011)

Antimicrobial sensitivity test antimicrobial susceptibility testing

In 0.45% saline, the 0.5 McFarland bacterial solution was diluted to 1.5 10⁷ CFU/ml. For cuddling and reading, cards are automatically filled, closed, and loaded into the VITEK 2. The combinations of medicines and microorganisms chosen for this study's performance evaluation of the VITEK 2 system were listed on the label for *staphylococcus*.

DNA Extraction and Molecular Identification

In order to collect the genomic DNA samples, a commercial DNA extraction technique was used. DNA was found utilizing gel electrophoresis and an ultraviolet (UV) transilluminator. The Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) method was used to identify the *clfA* genes in *S. aureus* bacterium. This primer was developed by the Canadian company Alpha DNA, according to table 1. The existence of amplified products was validated by 0.8% agarose gel electrophoresis to establish their presence. The gel was stained with 4 L of 10 mg/mL ethidium bromide for 1.5 hours at 70 v. (Sigma, USA). This method made use of a Gel Documentation System and a UV light transilluminator. The molecular weights of the amplified products were calculated using a 100bp ladder from Pioneer (Korea) (Levy *et al.*, 2008). There have been 5-min replication cycles at 95°C after a 5-min denaturation phase there, followed by 30-second temperature steps for certain genes and 50-second steps at 72°C, before such a final 10-min elongation step there.

Table 1. Primers utilized in the current investigation

Primer Type	Primer Sequence	Amplicon Size (bp)	Reference
<i>clfA</i>	F- ATTCTGCTGTTAAAGGTGACACAT	657	(Yousefi <i>et al.</i> , 2016)
	R- GTGTTGTAATTTGATCATCAGCGC		

Isolation and diagnosis

Insulation

Obtaining 5 isolates of *Staphylococcus aureus* that cause urinary tract infections from a total of 30 samples of patients carrying urinary catheters and urine in medical laboratories, their ages ranged between 30-80 years from meals and furniture, 17 samples from meals and 13 samples from females for a period of 12/15/ 2021 until the end of February 15, 2022, and samples were collected after placing the catheter tube for more than 4 hours, because the more the catheter was placed, it was observed that it appeared in dense bacterial growth, and this indicates that it helps in the growth of bacteria and their numbers, as well as after infection with urinary tract infection urea.

Diagnosis of bacterial isolates to identify bacterial isolates

Five isolates of *Staphylococcus aureus* were isolated and diagnosed initially on Maconkey agar and blood agar media, based on the diagnostic and differential characteristics of the bacteria. Stacks on the microscopic characteristics of bacterial cells, morphology and culture, including colony size, color and edge, and biochemical tests that diagnose each bacterial diagnosis and conformity to what is known by its name.

Diagnostic diagnosis of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates, a compressed Vitek 2 system was used, and after diagnosis, 5 isolates of bacteria were developed from the total of other names that contain 30 samples. cumbersome and imprecisely inefficient. Demonstrates tests in the Vitek 2 Compact Diagnostic System. They can be diagnosed using the integrated Vitek 2 System to provide confirmation findings for the identification of different isolates of bacteria. (in Turton *et al.*, 2008).

Antibiotic susceptibility test results using the Vitek 2 compact system

Antimicrobial susceptibility tests were tested in which 0.50McFarland bacterial suspension was diluted to 1.50x10⁷ CFU/mL in 0.45% saline. For reading and snuggling, the cards are automatically loaded, closed, and filled into the VITEK 2. This entire series of caverns.

Detection of the *clfA* gene

There were 4 different *S. aureus* isolates, according to the results., with a rate of 80%, that were carriers of the *clfA* gene, depending on the appearance of a bundle of 657 base pairs Figure 1, and these results were close to what was reached by (Yousefi *et al.* 2016) and

(Maki *et al.* 2022), respectively, where the percentage of gene presence was 100% and 100%. The number of isolates used, as well as their geographic and biological characteristics, varied between the current study and earlier ones, which is why the results were different.

Table 2 Antibiotic susceptibility test results

Antibiotic	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5
Benzylpenicillin	R	R	R	R	R
oxacillin	R	R	R	R	R
gentamicin	R	S	I	S	R
tobramycin	R	S	R	S	I
levofloxacin	R	S	R	R	R
erythromycin	R	R	R	R	R
clindamycin	R	R	R	R	R
trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole	S	S	R	R	R
tetracycline	R	S	R	R	R
fusidic acid	R	S	R	R	R

Figure 1. Electrophoresis of the product of the PCR reaction to detect the *clfA* gene

Sequence determination of the *clfA* gene

A single-sample PCR sequence for the *clfA* gene was sequenced from each sample's PCR reaction with the gene-specific primer at Macrogen, South Korea. Sequence analysis interactions after analysis on the NCBI blast site indicated that the amplified products of one sample contained the amplification product of size 1122 base pairs, where the results showed matching with (ID: [CP042081.1](#)) Figure 2, with size 1147, and with a percentage of 98%. This result is possible due to the presence of specific phylogenetic similarity or divergence in the hypothetical target sequences of this isolate. By comparing the sequences of these genes with the reference sequences on the NCBI site, the exact sites and details of the amplification plots for each gene were identified.

Figure 2 Comparison of the nitrogen base alignment of *Staphylococcus aureus* with (ID: CP042081.1) from the GenBank for the *clfA* gene

Discussion

Out of the total number of various antibiotics utilized in the study, which included antibiotics, the results revealed that 5 isolates were multi-resistant to antibiotics.

1. Indiscriminate or excessive use of antibiotics or misuse of antibiotics led to the transmission of this resistance by genetic factors or as a result of a change in the permeable wall of the bacterial cell.
2. Synthesis of degradative enzymes the β -lactam ring present in the antibiotic formulation of the beta-lactam group.
3. Owning a wallet, or owning Efflux pumps.
4. Its composition of the biofilm that surrounds the groups or colonies of bacterial cells to provide them with a kind of protection that largely prevents the penetration of the antibiotic dose and its access to the bacterial cell because it is a sticky substance.

5. A change in the permeability of the bacterial cell membrane, as the membrane contains protein channels called porins that block or prevent the passage of the antibody molecule into the bacterial cell and its access to its work site.
6. A chromosome mutation or resistance may be carried on a plasmid that encodes multiple antibiotic resistance
7. The bacteria are carriers of pathogenic islands acquired from nosocomial infections, which are adsorbed by many bacteria, especially *Staphylococcus aureus*.

The emergence of multiple resistance to antibiotics has become a global concern, as bacteria have become multiple mechanisms of antibiotic resistance through indiscriminate use and lack of health awareness, which has affected the emergence of resistant strains that have flow systems and their ability to change the permeability barrier and produce beta-lactamase enzymes, which made it a big problem that is increasing. This made it difficult to choose the appropriate treatment for her.

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